

Implementation of Citizenship Education Function as a Media for Political Education in Educational Institute (A Study at SMAN 1 Cikalong Wetan)

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: March 22 ,2026</p> <p>Accepted: June 20, 2026</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20691564</p> <p>Keywords : Internalization, Political Education, Citizenship Education, Citizenship Knowledge</p>	<p><i>This study described and analyzed PPKn's teachers' strategies to internalize political education through Citizenship Education subject. This study focused on constraints and solutions within the implementation of Citizenship Education in internalizing political education. This type of study was descriptive qualitative. The subjects of this study were the PPKn teachers and students of SMAN 1 Cikalong Wetan. Data collection was carried out through interview, observation, and documentation. The results showed some points. First, the efforts of PPKn teachers to internalize political education through Citizenship Education subject at SMAN 1 Cikalong Wetan was done by providing practices, such as general election simulation. This way was carried out in order that students could know how to step ahead when the election had taken place, so that students could actively participate in it and students participate active in elections. Second, the constraints faced by PPKn teachers in internalizing political education through Citizenship Education subject at SMAN 1 Cikalong Wetan were classified as internal and external obstacles. Third, the solution undertaken by PPKn teachers to face the constraints in internalizing political education through citizenship education subject at SMAN 1 Cikalong Wetan was carried out by increasing exemplary (model), effectiveness, creativity, and giving any comprehension.</i></p>

Introduction

The era of New Order had left a profound problem for the Indonesian, namely the political inadequacy of the majority of citizens as a result of the systematic depoliticization process carried out by the New Order regime. Increasing adequate knowledge and ability about democracy, forming a democratic attitude, being critical, having a courage to exercise control and upholding truth and justice, and feeling less concerned are naturally matters to face depoliticization (Cholisin, 2004, p. 55). This depoliticization process causes people tend to be passive and easy to mobilize by the authorities. The passive character of citizens with no independency and easiness to mobilize are constraints for democracy in Indonesia (Rohmawati, 2012, p. 1).

In a democratic country, people must understand and comprehend politics. In the era of globalization (openness), Indonesia provides the widest possible freedom for citizens to do certain politics. The freedom is the rights of the citizens (Sabela & Pritaningtias, 2017, p. 82), so that government must take political education that fosters the community seriously. Political education is essentially part of adult education as an intentional, deliberative, and systematic educational effort to form politically aware individuals with their capability to be politically responsible actors as well as being ethical and morally to achieve political goals (Kartono, 2009, p. 64).

Furthermore, political education has an important role in creating a politically literate nation and shaping character and behavior of citizens. Political education enables students to learn how efficient they become citizen in a state by involving their knowledge and skills (Kuş&Tarhan, 2016, p. 465). Besides, political education has a potency to shape character, behavior, and responsibility of citizens in order that they can achieve more advanced civilization (Sanusi, 2016, p. 24).

One of efforts to foster younger generation in the political field is through political education in school. Students will gain a lot of knowledge about politics and their role in it. Schools have an important role in shaping attitudes and behavior of citizens (Rohmawati, 2012, p. 2). Citizenship education subject is one of subjects in every level of school which has a correlation with political fields and its condition in Indonesia. Through this subject, students can gain knowledge and understanding of politics. Basically, this subject specifically educate students to be good citizenship, because the materials (topics) of the subject are dominantly political education.

In school, a subject which relates to political education is Pancasila and Citizenship Education with its main competencies, namely civic knowledge, civic skills, and civic values (civic disposition) (Branson, 1999, p. 4). In this subject, students can learn a lot of political knowledge, values, attitudes, and behavior. Besides, they can learn their rights and obligations as citizens, political systems, regional autonomy, political parties, political

culture, and many others. By this subject, students are expected to be able to actively participate in nation's and state's importance (Wahyuningsih, 2013, p. 11).

Pancasila and Citizenship Education (further abbreviated as PPKn) is a subject that has a mission as political education. As a statement of Soedijarto (Cholisin, 2010, p. 2), that PPKn subject aims to develop good citizens; that is citizens who can participate actively and responsibly in the scope of nation's and state's importance. Yet, contrary, the current students' behavior has not reflected democratic attitudes and behaviors. It signifies that political education has not been successful to form and develop a democratic culture.

In more deeply, the role of PPKn's teachers to internalize political education through Citizenship Education learning should be taken into consideration. Therefore, this study attempts to describe and analyze PPKn's teachers' strategies to internalize political education through Citizenship Education subject. To make it in a comprehensive layout, this study specifies its discussion into some focuses, namely constrains and solution within the implementation of Citizenship Education in internalizing political education.

Research Methodology

This study used descriptive method with qualitative approach to describe deeply the phenomena and symptoms that occur based on facts investigated in this study. Qualitative research method is a research method based on the philosophy of post-positivism that is to examine the condition of a natural object. It emphasizes on meaning of any fact being studied (Sugiyono, 2017, p. 9). Therefore, the selection of this method was considered appropriate, because the focus of this research is interpreting and deeply observing civic knowledge as an effort to improve political education.

Results and Discussion

Efforts of PPKn teachers in internalizing political education through Citizenship Education learning at SMAN 1 Cicalong Wetan

The PPKn teachers to internalize political education through Citizenship Education learning at SMAN 1 Cicalong Wetan was that PPKn teachers have carried out many things (special efforts), such as providing the learning material, and students were given tasks about political education. This condition has been similarly state in Law No. 14 of 2005 that teachers are professional educators with the main task of educating, teaching, guiding, directing, training, assessing, and evaluating students in every level of education (primary, secondary, and high school). These ways were carried out in order that students can have an advance understanding on the importance of political education. After students have understood political education, an awareness will grow in themselves. They will practice themselves in their own environment, such as school environment and community environment.

In the process of political education, teachers act as a holder and conveyor of values and views on political education. Besides, they are creator and manipulator of learning culture. The learning habits of students in the classroom will indirectly address political consequences. Meanwhile, the task of teachers' teaching is related to value transformation and personal formation, while teaching assignments are related to the transformation of knowledge and skills for students. A study has implicated that political education is urgent for young people to prepare themselves to participate in any political condition, particularly general election which requires their ideas in order that they can decide their choice very well (Neundorf & Smets, 2017, p. 8)

The previous phenomenon is in accordance with Article 20 Law No. 14 of 2005 concerning teachers and lecturers' duties as follows:

- 1) Plan a learning, carry out a qualified learning process, assess and evaluate learning outcomes;
- 2) Improve and develop academic qualifications and competencies on an ongoing basis in regards to the development of science, technology and arts;
- 3) Maintain and cultivate unity and integrity of nation. Teacher has a responsibility; not only conveying ideas, but also representing a creative way of life and a symbol of peace and tranquility in anxiety and persecution, so that teachers are said as guardians of civilization and protectors of advancement of progress (Siswoyo, 2007, p. 133).

Another effort of PPKn teachers to internalize political education is by providing practices, such as general election simulation. In this term of practice, students will follow it in order that they can know how to step ahead when the general election takes place, so that they can actively participate in the election process. Therefore, by providing reinforcement of PPKn materials which relate to political education with any possible method are considerable ways that teachers can carry out.

Constrains in internalizing political education through Citizenship Education learning at SMAN 1 Cicalong Wetan

Internal Constrains

The PPKn teachers have found variety of obstacles; one of which was difficulties to provide number of exemplary to students in implementing political education. One of the difficulties experienced by teachers was unstable condition of the state. In this case, Sunarso (2007, p. 22) states that the condition of state's politics

influences the progress of education. Therefore, in regards to it, the PPKn teachers can be professional teachers when they have some competency, namely: (a) understanding and comprehending material (topic), structure (form), concepts, and pattern of scientific thought that possibly support the subject; (b) understanding the substance of the subject which includes civic knowledge, civic values, civic disposition, and civic skills; and (c) be able to demonstrate the benefits of the subject. Thus, any inspiration (as role model) greatly influences the development of students in internalizing political values that have been transformed through the Pancasila and Citizenship Education subject.

External Constrains

1. Limited Learning Time Allocation

There have been a quite number of topics in PPKn subject with a learning time allocation of only 2 hours (2 x 45 minutes) per week for the upper secondary level. It becomes constrain for the implementation of the development of political education carried out in teaching and learning activities. This time allocation has been in relevant to the Regulation of the Ministry of Education and Culture No. 22 of 2016 concerning Standard of Primary and Secondary Education Process which states that the allocation of *face-to-face* learning time allocation for secondary education is 45 minutes. If there are 2 hours of lesson each week, the total learning time is only 90 minutes. The allocation of learning time is felt to be insufficient with the Pancasila and Citizenship Education (PPKn) subject. In the same context, Cholisin (2010:8-9) argues that as a formal political education, the PPKn certainly bring any consequence of topics that is not only in accordance to the values of politics, but also scientific structure of politics into *civic knowledge, civic skills (intellectual skills and participation skills), and civic dispositions*

2. External Negative Influences

The existence of external negative influences that occur in society is one of constrains that the PPKn teachers face when they are developing political education in teaching and learning activities in the classroom. This is exemplified by some cases, such as corruption of state's officials and official distortion. These case certainly affect students' way of thinking in understanding politics, law, and morals that are being taught in school. In addition, Cholisin (2000, p. 8) argues that a form of public direct socialization is carried out when someone accepts and learn the values of information, attitude, perspectives, and beliefs about politics explicitly.

3. Different Background of Students

The different background of students are also constrains faced by the PPKn teachers. The background can include family condition, friendship, and environment where they live. A variety of backgrounds that does not support political climate can hinder PPKn teachers from developing political education. In this matter, Cholisin (2000, p. 6) argues that the political learning method that can be used to support political learning through PPKn subjects is by following parents' choice and local figures' choice. These two elements have sufficiently become the basic capitals to communicate and mobilize masses movement (choice).

Solutions carried out by PPKn Teachers to face constrains when internalizing political education through Citizenship Education Learning at SMAN 1 Cikalong Wetan

Overcoming Internal Constrains

A teacher must be an exemplary figure for students. They are likely a role model with a high morale and religious values that should be emulated and exemplified by students (Suparlan, 2006, pp. 33-34). To be an exemplary figure, a teacher needs to perform good attitude and behavior, noble character, and noble morals (e.g. honest, diligent, willing to learn, trustworthy, social and courteous to others). Besides, a teacher should try to carry out noble values instilled in students' personality. In this matter, Cholisin (2011, p. 19) construes that teachers should be able to be an exemplary figure for students. It implies that the attitude and action of teacher automatically describe the characters that are internalized to students.

Overcoming External Constrains

1. The Increase of Teachers Effectiveness and Creativity in Learning Process

The allocation of learning time is constrainfaced by the PPKn teachers in the founding of political education in teaching and learning activities in the classroom. In overcoming the 90 minutes (2x45 minutes) allocation of learning time for PPKn subjects, they have an intention to increase their effectiveness and creativity in the learning process. Teachers are required to be able to develop teaching materials, methods, and learning media that can ease students to understand and comprehend the materials being taught with the time allocated. Similar to this evidence, a study has addressed that in learning, teachers must have ability to select, organize, and package, learning materials into a depth scope in accordance with curricular goals, and have the ability to grab a power to influence students in order that they can digest the materials deliberated by their teachers (Hamdayana, 2016, p. 12). Thus, learning process attracts the attention of students with a straightforward explanation, so that students can understand the materials easily.

2. Teacher Gives Understanding

The way that PPKn teachers can overcome constraints related to negative influences from external aspect and the different backgrounds of students, has affected the process of developing political education in teaching and learning activities in the classroom. It is carried out by providing an understanding and exemplary that are easy for participants to understand. According to Suparlan (2006, pp. 33-34), as a guide, a teacher needs to have an ability to guide students and provide psychological encouragement, so that students can put aside internal and external factors that will interfere with learning process wholly in schools, as well as providing direction and career development for students in accordance with their talents and abilities.

Furthermore, current understanding and attitude are needed in training students to see the condition of students with their lack to internalize good values, so the role of the teacher as a demonstrator is highly needed. To respond it, a study has indicated that the teacher's role as a demonstrator is to show students on everything that makes students comprehensive and able to understand any message conveyed (Sanjaya, 2008, pp. 281-290). Thus, providing an understanding and attitude about something good and bad will certainly uncover students' understanding, so that it will help students achieve the expected goals in the founding of political education.

Conclusion

This study has some points to implicate. First, the PPKn teacher efforts to internalize political education through Citizenship Education subject at SMAN 1 Cikalong Wetan is carried out by providing reinforcement of PPKn materials that relate to political education as well as using methods that possibly lead to political education.

Second, the constraints faced by teachers in internalizing political education through Citizenship Education subject are divided into internal and external obstacles. Internally, teachers have difficulty to set an exemplary model (figure), while externally can involve the limited time allocation of learning and the negative influence that can resemble corruption and abuse of power that can possibly influence students to understand political education.

Third, the solutions made by the PPKn teachers to face constraints in internalizing political education through Citizenship Education subject are categorized into internal and external solution. These kinds of solutions are spoken out by referring to the obstacles. Internally, teachers increase an exemplary by carrying out some possible internalized values, increasing effectiveness and creativity by using methods and media that are in accordance with material demands as well as providing a comprehension through any existing exemplary that are easily understood by students. Meanwhile, the external solution is carried out by providing appropriate understanding to students related to political education.

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